

Evaluation of Surgical Outcomes and Recurrence Rates in Non-Melanoma Skin Cancers: A Single Center Retrospective Study

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Submitted: 01/04/2025 Accepted: 16/04/2025 published: 19/04/2025

Citation: Ahmet Korur S. , Erkin Unlu R., Murat Ergani H., Sahin O., Evaluation of Surgical Outcomes and Recurrence Rates in Non-Melanoma Skin Cancers: A Single Center Retrospective Study, (2025), Med Biomedical J., 2(4), 1-4

Abstract

Background:

Non-melanoma skin cancers (NMSC), including basal cell carcinoma (BCC) and squamous cell carcinoma (SCC), are the most common malignancies worldwide, particularly affecting the head and neck. BCC is locally invasive, while SCC carries a higher risk of metastasis. Surgical excision remains the primary treatment, and achieving clear histopathological margins is critical in minimizing recurrence.

Objective:

This study seeks to assess recurrence rates and surgical margin positivity in patients treated for non-melanoma skin cancer (NMSC) and to examine the correlation of these outcomes with age, gender, diagnosis, and lesion location.

Methods:

A retrospective analysis was conducted on 209 patients who underwent surgical excision for NMSC at Ankara Bilkent City Hospital between January 2022 and January 2023. Demographic data, diagnosis, surgical margins, and recurrence status were collected and evaluated over a one-year postoperative follow-up period.

Results:

There was no statistically significant association between local recurrence and lesion location, gender, or diagnosis. However, recurrence was significantly associated with older age ($p < 0.05$). Margin positivity was significantly related to diagnosis ($p < 0.05$), with higher rates observed in BCC patients. Logistic regression analysis confirmed diagnosis as an independent predictor of margin positivity. Among patients pre-diagnosed with BCC but pathologically confirmed with SCC, local recurrence was higher, likely due to inadequate excision margins. Conversely, patients initially diagnosed with SCC but pathologically confirmed with BCC had no recurrence.

Conclusion:

Both patient age and diagnosis are key predictors of recurrence and margin positivity in NMSC. In particular, cases of diagnostic discrepancy highlight the importance of accurate preoperative evaluation and appropriate surgical planning. Elderly patients and those with BCC require careful surgical consideration to ensure complete excision while balancing aesthetic outcomes.

Keywords: Non-melanoma skin cancer, Surgical Margins, Local Recurrence, Plastic Surgery.

1. Introduction

Non-melanoma skin cancers are the most common malignancies worldwide, affecting the head and neck region the most. Basal Cell Carcinoma (BCC) accounts for 75-80% of these cancers, Squamous Cell Carcinoma (SCC) comprises 20-25%, and rarely, Merkel Cell Carcinoma (MCC) represents less than 5%. While BCC is locally aggressive, SCC has a greater potential for metastasis. MCC is a neuroendocrine tumor characterized by elevated mortality rates and an unfavorable prognosis.

The mechanism of skin carcinogenesis remains incompletely elucidated. (1–3) Numerous studies have been undertaken to elucidate the mechanisms that contribute to malignancy. As plastic surgeons, we must be proficient in managing this cancer. A variety of treatments are available for these tumors, such as phototherapy, radiation therapy, electrocryotherapy, brachytherapy, Mohs surgery, and topical agents; nevertheless, the primary treatment remains surgical excision (4, 5).

Non-melanoma skin cancers exhibit a low metastasis rate and favorable prognosis; specifically, basal cell carcinoma (BCC) has a metastasis rate of under 1% over five years, whereas squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) may range from 5% to 8%. A prior study established that the recurrence rates for non-melanoma skin cancer were 3.6% for basal cell carcinoma (BCC) and 3.4% for squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) at the 5-year follow-up post-treatment. (7,8)

This study aims to gather data on the epidemiology of non-melanoma skin cancers and evaluate the rate of local recurrence following surgery, dependent on a positive margin on any side or a 1 mm surgical margin post-treatment. (8)

2. Material and Methods

This is a retrospective study carried out from March 2024 to April 2024. Patients diagnosed with non-melanoma skin cancer were observed in the outpatient clinic for one year following surgical intervention at Ankara Bilkent City Hospital. The study included patients who underwent surgery from January 2022 to January 2023. Data obtained from the hospital's database were acquired. Patients were evaluated according to archive number, first name, last name, gender, age, preliminary diagnosis, definitive diagnosis, pathology results, and recurrence. Patients with pre-diagnosed or diagnosed cancerous tissues underwent excision in the operating room under local or general anesthesia, ensuring a surgical margin of at least 5 mm, followed by reconstruction of the defects using skin grafts or local flaps. Patients were subsequently scheduled for follow-up evaluations at 1 month, 3 months, 6 months, and 1 year, during which they were assessed alongside the pathology results.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted utilizing SPSS version 25.0 software (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), median (range), or count and frequency, as applicable. Variables were assessed through chi-square and logistic regression analysis. The data is determined to be normally distributed.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

Undeclared.

3. Results

The statistical analysis of this study revealed no statistically significant differences in local recurrence concerning lesion location ($p = 0.823$), patient gender ($p = 0.645$), or patient diagnosis ($p = 0.549$). Similarly, there is no significant distinction between local recurrence and positive surgical margins ($p = 0.925$). A statistically significant difference was observed between local recurrence and patient age ($p < 0.05$).

About the surgical margin positivity, no significant difference was found between the location of the lesions ($p = 0.925$), gender of the patients ($p = 0.607$), or age of the patients ($p = 0.463$). In contrast, a significant difference was found between surgical margin positivity and the diagnosis received by the patients ($p < 0.05$).

The logistic regression analysis demonstrated a statistically significant reduction in the likelihood of positive surgical margins associated with the patients' diagnosis (OR = 0.333, 95% CI [0.204, 0.543], $p < 0.05$), even when adjusting for gender and lesion location. The findings indicate that the patients' diagnosis serves as a predictor of surgical margin positivity, independent of other demographic and clinical variables.

4. DISCUSSION

Previous studies indicate that the gender distribution in non-melanoma skin cancers predominantly features male patients, with an average age of 70 years (59.2%). A separate study indicated that the majority were female (53%) (7, 8). This study's primary demographic consisted of males (51.2%), with a mean age of 69.5 years among participants. The findings of this study align with those of other research. Non-melanoma skin cancers predominantly occur on the face. In this study, it is also found that 91% of the patients' lesions were on the face, 6.22% on the upper extremity, 1.44% on the body, and 0.96% on the lower extremity. This phenomenon can be elucidated by prior research indicating that cancers are more prevalent in regions exposed to sunlight (9–11).

No statistically significant difference was observed between the lesion locations and the patients' gender, diagnosis, or age. ($p < 0.05$) Of the 163 patients pre-diagnosed with BCC, 110 (52.6%) were confirmed to have BCC, 21 (10.05%) were diagnosed with SCC, and 32 (15.3%) were identified with non-melanoma skin cancer. Among 39 patients pre-diagnosed with SCC, 22 (10.5%) were confirmed to have SCC, 8 (3.8%) were diagnosed with BCC, and 9 (4.3%) were identified with non-melanoma skin cancer.

Seven patients were diagnosed with non-melanoma skin cancer; four (1.91%) were diagnosed with non-melanoma skin cancer, three (1.44%) with basal cell carcinoma (BCC), and none with squamous cell carcinoma (SCC). Local recurrence occurred in 1 (4.54%) of the 22 patients initially diagnosed with BCC, who were subsequently diagnosed with SCC following pathology results.

In patients pre-diagnosed with BCC, where pathology results indicate SCC, excisions may be conducted without adequate surgical margins, potentially resulting in undesirable local recurrences. Another result corroborating this finding is that none of the eight patients pre-diagnosed with SCC, whose pathological results indicated BCC, experienced local recurrence. The outcome may indicate that in patients with SCC prior to diagnosis, excision of the masses with broader resection yields adequate margins for lesions with BCC pathology results. Studies indicate that the most prevalent tumors were basal cell carcinoma (BCC), with an incidence rate of 3.6%. In these studies, a surgical margin of 3.8 mm was established as the criterion, and some authors indicated that the recurrence rate of tumors could be diminished by securing broader surgical margins (7,8).

The surgical margin criterion was 5.0, with local recurrence rates of 3.35% for basal cell carcinoma (BCC) and 1.91% for squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) after one year of follow-up. A statistically significant rise in local recurrence was observed in patients aged 75-99, while the incidence of local recurrence appeared to diminish in the age group of 25-74. ($p < 0.05$). However, certain studies indicate that the recurrence rate correlates with tumor depth and is independent of age and gender (12–14).

Among 12 patients with local recurrence, 83.33% of the lesions were located on the face, 16.67% on the upper extremity, and there were no lesions with local recurrence in the lower extremity. Surgeons refrain from making radical incisions in the facial region due to cosmetic standards, while no local recurrence was observed in the lower extremity, as incisions in these areas pose fewer aesthetic concerns. No statistically significant difference was noted among patients with positive margin status regarding lesion location, gender, and age. However, a statistically significant difference found between the patients with positive margin status and their diagnoses. ($p < 0.05$). Among patients with positive margins, 74.65% were diagnosed with BCC and 23.9% with SCC; the incidence of positive margins was five times higher in patients with BCC compared to those with SCC. This indicates that 57.89% of the patients in this study were diagnosed with BCC, while only 20.57% were diagnosed with SCC.

In patients with positive margins, inadequate excision is the predominant cause of local recurrence and margin positivity. Although local recurrence correlates with tumor characteristics and localization, it is also associated with the patient's age. (15,16)

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5. Conclusion

Non-melanoma skin cancer is a concern that plastic surgeons and patients must approach with caution. Surgeons must exercise caution during lesion excision, and the patient should not disregard outpatient clinic follow-ups. Patients should be cognizant that 80% of individuals referred to the plastic surgery clinic with a pre-diagnosis of skin cancer subsequently received a confirmed diagnosis of skin cancer. Particularly elderly individuals should be cautioned that their diagnosis may arise during outpatient clinic follow-up. The primary objective should be to achieve clean surgical margins, rather than prioritizing the patient's cosmetic appearance.

We also acknowledge the productive interinstitutional collaboration between ISSSTE and IMSS facilities in Uruapan and Morelia, Michoacán, Mexico. This partnership exemplifies the power of institutional cooperation in advancing medical research and improving patient care in our region.

Special recognition is due to the clinical staff who facilitated patient interactions and data collection, as well as to the administrative personnel who provided essential logistical support. Their collective efforts were instrumental in the completion of this research project.

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